

Companion Planting in the school garden

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Abstract

We would like to report and share our knowledge and practice from the school garden, regarding companion planting, that is “planting together with benefits”. Under our standard cultivating year-round approach, working on “seed to seed” activities, we prepare our seed plants in the greenhouse, later to be transplanted to the garden raised beds in a companion planting mode, enhancing the benefits of companionship and biodiversity in action. We have tested many combinations over the last 12 years, as knowledge and practice is also passed on to us by older classmates and community members and we have found out that some combinations can actually help one or more of the companions flourish. Our vegetable crops are getting better and we are happy to have more quality products to share within the community.

Keywords: companion planting; school garden; garden-based teaching and learning; biodiversity; STEM & environmental science education; active & responsible citizenship

Introduction

The arrangement of crops in a way they complement each other in collaborative mode is known as “companion planting”. Plants that have different requirements for nutrients, sunlight and cultivating space, often make good “garden buddies”, much like “plant families” and “plant communities”. The project activities are situated in the school garden and within the community interactions amongst parents, local agents and stakeholders. The activities are

Our motto for companion planting is: **"Every plant is valuable! Every plant contributes!"**, thus we see it much like our communities of people. When we collaborate in groups and we respect each other, we can work miracles and we can all benefit together. We started by designing and implementing the plant arrangements in the raised beds of the school garden, bearing in mind some of the basic principles of companion planting, such as:

- **Sunlight:** some plants are more sun worshippers, while others are rather shade lovers, e.g. tall crops, such as peas and corn can shade lettuce and spinach from the midday sun, extending the harvest season in late spring.
- **Nutrients and Water:** all plants need water and nutrients from the soil to survive, but not in the same way, e.g. corn, is a nitrogen hog, but carrots require much less of that nutrient. Some plants, such as squash, have deep roots that can pull nutrients and water from greater depths than onions, lettuce, and other shallow-rooted crops.
- **Good partnership:** the life cycles, growth rates, or temperature preferences differ and contribute, e.g. we can plant fast-growing, cool-weather crops like lettuce, radishes, or cilantro early in the season, alongside slower-growing, heat-loving tomatoes. We will be able to harvest our early crops quickly, making room for the tomatoes to take over later.

Implementation

Our efforts and explorations on companion planting have led us to create an effective cultivating practice and an increased crop production. Our “community of plants” in the school garden, following biodiversity and companionship principles, has proved to be viable and fruitful.

Let us tell you how we do companion planting in our school garden! First, we start with the seeds, because seeds are important! We make seed plants in the greenhouse and wait for them to stem and become little "baby plants". That might take 2 to 4 weeks. Then, we take them to the raised beds and plant them together in groups. **We might have 3 to 5 different plants in each raised bed.** We arrange them in rows depending on the size they get when they grow up.

We create "symbiotic relationships" in our school garden, since we carefully arrange the "planting buddies" together, in order to be in "good company". We and our plants have one common goal: to be friends and work together. We can all complete each, for our common benefit and prosperity.

We usually plant lettuce together with onions and radishes, as we found out that they are good garden buddies and companions. They also get along with Swiss chard pretty well!

We also plant onions with lettuce and tomatoes. Onions naturally keep away aphids and other pests. This means that good companion plants for onions are any plants that often fall victim to them. We plant fast-growing, cool-weather crops like lettuce or radishes early in spring together with slower-growing, heat-loving tomatoes. We will be able to harvest our early lettuce and radishes quickly, making room for the tomatoes to take over their space later.

We usually plant basil near tomatoes. We can cook them together and make spaghetti sauce, but they also grow in harmony with each other. It is believed the aromatic oils in basil leaves keep insects away. Otherwise, they could come near and mess with the tomato plants. It looks like the basil is the tomato's bodyguard. Marigolds, garlic and onions keep insect pests away from crops because of their distinctive aromas, so it is nice to grow them in several locations in the garden.

Radishes, for example, may attract flea beetles and they can potentially become a "trap crop" for the rest of our plants. What we do is to leave a few radishes around the garden. Flea beetles love radishes and will get on them easily and eat their leaves instead of the broccoli, cauliflower or eggplants. When the insects are stacked and trapped on the radishes, we can take them away out of the garden. It appears that we can trick those insects and set "plant traps" for them!

We also conduct "fair tests" and companion planting explorations in our school garden. Suppose we have similar conditions in two garden beds: same size, same soil, same sunshine, same watering etc. In the first bed, we practice companion planting with: i.e. lettuce (romaine, green & red lollo), parsley and onions. But, in the second one we plant romaine lettuce alone.

This arrangement is depicted in the above two garden bed designs, respectively. Early spring is a proper time in the year to conduct this exploration in the school garden. Our fellow pupils have been doing explorations as such for the last decade or so and they have passed on to us valuable knowledge and practice. They have repeatedly claimed that the lettuce plants cultivated with other companion plants have grown big and healthy, whereas when cultivated alone, they often get pests, grow smaller and are not very tasty, in fact they are a bit bitter. But, we still have to conduct our exploration again this year and see if we can verify their claims.

Nevertheless, we have shared our findings and practice within the school, the teachers and parents, the local community, as well as with the collaborating school networks. We conduct meetings, presentations and even organize "garden fiestas". Moreover, we have shared our rich crop of vegetables with local welfare agents in community meals, through a collaboration framework with the Rethymno basketball team "Cretan Kings" and the "Cretan Kings Assist", the team community outreach program. We often donate a part of our crop to community families in need, in a gentle and discrete mode, for solidarity and social responsibility.

Conclusions

Companion planting in the school garden

	Basil	Beans	Broccoli	Carrots	Cauliflower	Chives	Cilantro	Corn	Cucumbers	Dill	Garlic	Leeks	Lettuce	Marigold	Melon	Nasturtium	Onion	Oregano	Parsley	Peas	Peppers	Rosemary	Sage	Spinach	Squash	Strawberries	Sunflowers	Swiss Chard	Thyme	Tomatoes	
Basil																															
Beans																															
Broccoli																															
Carrots																															
Cauliflower																															
Chives																															
Cilantro																															
Corn																															
Cucumber																															
Dill																															
Garlic																															
Leeks																															
Lettuce																															
Marigold																															
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Swiss Chard																															
Thyme																															
Tomatoes																															

■ Plants grow well together
 ■ Don't plant together!
 ■ Beneficial to garden in general
■ Combination helps bug control
 ■ Carrots will have good flavor, but stunted roots

It seems that the "lore", the mystery and the science of companion planting have intrigued and fascinated people for centuries, yet it is a part of the gardening world that has not been sufficiently explored. Even today, we appear to be just on the threshold of research. In years to come we hope that scientists, gardeners, and farmers everywhere will work together in making more discoveries that will prove of great value in augmenting the world's food supply. We believe that citizens' science and knowledge can help in that direction, as well. Thus, we continue to test our ideas through applications and explorations in our school garden.

Plants that assist each other to grow well, plants that repel insects, even plants that repel other plants, all are of great practical use. They always have been, but we are just beginning to find out why. Delving deeply into this fascinating aspect of gardening can provide for us both pleasure and very useful knowledge to develop and share.

For example, we have noticed repeatedly, that broccoli are good garden buddies with lettuce, onions, spinach, dill and Swiss chard, whereas they also appear to benefit from the oregano and thyme plants we have around the garden. Tomatoes, on the other hand, are not good garden buddies with broccoli, cauliflower, dill and corn, whereas they are good companions with lettuce, beans, onions, garlic, parsley, peppers, as well as with marigolds and basil (their "bodyguard"). As for the carrots, to come back to our initial question, the above chart indicates that when cultivated near tomatoes, they *"will have good flavor, but stunted roots"*. Well, we insisted in cultivating tomatoes and carrots together in a rich soil, with plenty of the compost mixture we produce in our school garden, from organic matter and plants leftover. Our carrots grow big and tasty and our tomatoes are aromatic and rather sweet. Perhaps it is the soil factor that makes a difference or maybe the local climate conditions of the Northern part of Crete, or even the "plants community" we have in our school garden. We need to explore further ...

Meanwhile, perhaps you would like to enjoy our "companion planting song", or click on the following link to hear us singing it [<https://youtu.be/mkgWn8oNW2k>]:

Seed to seed, cheek to cheek
In our garden plants can meet
Garden buddies, oh so sweet!
Seed to seed, they'll never quit!
Seed to seed, our crops grow big!

Every plant is valuable
Every plant contributes
If you find which match the most
You'll grow your harvest at no cost
Biodiversity works and rocks!

Seed to seed, cheek to cheek
In our garden plants can meet
Maybe we should be upbeat:
Good bedfellows can make it!
Companion planting can't be a myth!

We have also created a video on "companion planting", at our school garden. You can follow the link [<https://youtu.be/D134YI3T19o>] and watch it from the YouTube channel of the Primary Science Laboratory at the 9th Primary School of Rethymno, Crete, Greece.

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